

SANE: A Neural Surrogate for Accelerated Multi-Topology Analog Circuit Simulation

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Abstract

Analog circuit simulation with numerical ODE solvers is reliable, but repeated transient analysis can be too slow for parameter sweeps, tolerance studies, and design iteration. This paper presents **SANE** (**S**urrogate for **A**nalog **N**eural **E**mulation), a single shared neural surrogate trained to emulate transient waveforms across **21 analog circuit topologies**. A dataset of 176 100 simulated waveform pairs is constructed, spanning passive filters, diode and transistor circuits, operational amplifier stages, and switching converters. SANE reaches a mean NRMSE of 8.39% across all topologies on the held-out test set. After training, inference takes 0.127 ms per sample on an RTX 5090, compared with milliseconds to tens of seconds per sample for the reference ODE solver on a single CPU core, corresponding to a mean speed-up of about $\sim 38,000\times$ across the library. A full-dataset ablation study evaluates the effect of training loss design and backbone architecture choice.

Keywords: analog circuit simulation, neural surrogate model, temporal convolutional network, multi-topology emulation, machine learning for EDA

1. Introduction

Analog circuit simulation is central to electronic design automation (EDA). Standard tools such as SPICE [1] compute transient responses by solving the circuit equations numerically. The results are accurate, but repeated transient simulation becomes expensive in parameter sweeps, optimisation, and Monte Carlo analysis. In our circuit library, a simple RC network runs in a

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few milliseconds, while a stiff oscillator can take tens of seconds (Table 1). This runtime gap matters in Monte Carlo analysis, parameter sweeps, optimisation, and real-time or interactive use.

One way around this cost is to replace the numerical solver with a learned surrogate [2]. Prior work in analog circuit design has applied Gaussian-process-based surrogate and optimisation methods [3], machine-learning-driven global optimisation frameworks [4], and neural networks for transient circuit modelling [5]. Most of these models are trained for a single circuit or a narrow family of circuits. That limits their usefulness in practice, because a new surrogate must usually be trained whenever the topology changes.

This paper studies a harder setting: one neural surrogate for a diverse library of analog circuits. We train a single neural network to emulate transient waveforms for 21 circuit topologies simultaneously, spanning passive filters, diode and transistor circuits, operational amplifier stages, and switching converters.

The paper makes two main contributions. First, it shows that a single shared surrogate can be trained and evaluated across 21 heterogeneous analog circuit topologies, providing a practical speed-up for forward waveform prediction. Second, it contributes a large heterogeneous benchmark dataset of 176 100 waveform pairs and a full-dataset ablation study examining the effect of loss design and backbone architecture on multi-topology surrogate accuracy.

The remainder of the paper describes the circuit library, dataset, model, training setup, experiments, and limitations.

2. Related Work

2.1. Surrogate Models for Circuit Simulation

Model order reduction (MOR) has a long history in circuit simulation. Projection-based methods such as PRIMA [6] and SPRIM [7] construct compact linear models from full-order netlist matrices, enabling fast frequency-domain analysis. Nonlinear MOR extensions [8] apply trajectory piece-wise linearisation to handle switching and nonlinear devices, but still require per-topology model construction. Rational transfer function approximation methods, such as vector fitting [9], identify compact frequency-domain macromodels from port data, but are limited to linear time-invariant topologies and fixed operating conditions.

Early data-driven surrogate approaches applied response surface methods [10] and Gaussian process regression [11] to map circuit parameters to scalar performance metrics (e.g., gain, bandwidth). These methods scale poorly to high-dimensional input spaces and cannot produce full time-domain waveforms.

Neural network-based emulators have been proposed for specific circuit classes: feed-forward networks for DC operating point prediction in transistor circuits [12], neural networks for transient circuit modelling [5], and physics-informed networks that embed Kirchhoff’s laws as constraints [13, 14]. Within the analog circuit domain, most published methods remain topology-specific or target scalar performance metrics rather than full transient waveforms across a diverse circuit library. SANE addresses this gap by training a single model across 21 topologies. Spectral regularisation terms are also evaluated as an additional training objective, though the ablation study in Section 8.3 shows they do not improve accuracy in this setting.

Recent work has further expanded the scope of neural surrogates for circuit and converter design. Fan et al. [15] proposed a Graph-Transformer-based surrogate for converter topology design that generalises to unseen topologies while substantially accelerating evaluation relative to high-fidelity simulation. Ho et al. [16] introduced LASANA, a large-scale surrogate modelling framework for analog sub-blocks in neuromorphic architecture exploration, demonstrating substantial speed gains over conventional circuit simulation. DeepONet-based approaches have also been explored for dynamic behaviour modelling of analog circuits [17]. These studies reflect growing interest in generalisable surrogate models beyond single-topology settings, closely aligned with the multi-topology goal of the present work.

2.2. Temporal Convolutional Networks

Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs), introduced in [18], use dilated causal convolutions to model long-range temporal dependencies without recurrence. TCNs have demonstrated competitive or superior performance to LSTMs on sequence modelling benchmarks while offering parallelisable training. Their fixed receptive field and causality property make them particularly suitable for real-time signal processing applications, including audio synthesis [19] and time-series forecasting [18].

2.3. Multi-Resolution Spectral Loss

Spectral losses based on the STFT have been used in audio synthesis [20, 21] to enforce accurate frequency-domain behaviour. We include multi-resolution STFT terms in the training loss as an additional regulariser; however, as the ablation study in Section 8.3 shows, these terms do not improve average accuracy in this multi-topology setting.

2.4. Surrogate-Based Optimisation

Bayesian optimisation [22] and evolutionary algorithms [23] are standard tools for derivative-free circuit optimisation. When the surrogate model is differentiable, gradient-based optimisers such as Adam [24] can dramatically reduce the number of function evaluations required, since gradients with respect to circuit parameters are obtained by backpropagation through the surrogate—a strategy enabled by automatic differentiation tools [25, 26]. In its current form SANE does not receive explicit component parameters as model inputs, so direct gradient-based parameter search through the surrogate is not yet possible; this is identified as future work.

3. Circuit Library and Simulation Framework

3.1. Circuit Topologies

Table 1 lists the 21 circuit topologies included in SANE. They are organised into five families: passive filters, diode circuits, transistor stages, operational amplifier circuits, and switching power converters. Each circuit is implemented as a Python module that samples component values, builds the corresponding ODE system, and solves it with `scipy.integrate.solve_ivp` using Radau or LSODA.

3.2. Stimulus Types

Each simulation is driven by one of five stimulus types chosen uniformly at random: (1) *step* with random amplitude and rise time; (2) *sinusoid* with random amplitude, frequency, and phase; (3) *multi-sine* as a superposition of three to five sinusoids; (4) *band-limited noise* passed through a first-order Butterworth filter; and (5) *pulse-width modulated* (PWM) signal with random duty cycle and switching frequency. These stimulus types expose the model to several distinct waveform regimes rather than a single narrow input distribution.

Table 1: Circuit library: topologies, families, and approximate solver runtime per sample (single CPU core, 1024 time steps).

Circuit	Family	Speed group	Approx. runtime (ms)
RC Lowpass	Passive filter	Fast	~3
RC Highpass	Passive filter	Fast	~3
RLC Lowpass	Passive filter	Fast	~5
RLC Bandpass	Passive filter	Fast	~5
RLC Highpass	Passive filter	Slow	~600
LC Tank	Passive filter	Slow	~500
Diode Rectifier	Diode circuit	Fast	~8
Diode Clipper	Diode circuit	Fast	~8
Diode Clamper	Diode circuit	Medium	~80
BJT Common-Emitter	Transistor stage	Medium	~108
MOSFET Switch	Transistor stage	Medium	~60
Op-Amp Lowpass	Op-amp circuit	Fast	~12
Op-Amp Integrator	Op-amp circuit	Fast	~10
Op-Amp Differentiator	Op-amp circuit	Medium	~70
Sallen-Key LP	Op-amp circuit	Fast	~15
Sallen-Key HP	Op-amp circuit	Slow	~400
Buck Converter	Power converter	Medium	~200
Boost Converter	Power converter	Medium	~200
Buck-Boost Converter	Power converter	Medium	~200
Ćuk Converter	Power converter	Slow	~800
Wien-bridge Oscillator	Oscillator	Very slow	~98,000

3.3. Parameter Sampling

Component parameters are drawn from log-uniform prior distributions over physically realistic ranges. For example, resistances are sampled from $R \sim \mathcal{U}_{\log}[100 \Omega, 10 \text{ k}\Omega]$ and capacitances from $C \sim \mathcal{U}_{\log}[1 \text{ nF}, 10 \mu\text{F}]$. Log-uniform sampling ensures adequate coverage of both small and large parameter values, which span several orders of magnitude in practice [27].

4. Dataset Generation

4.1. Sample Budget and Split

The dataset contains 176 100 training samples distributed across the 21 circuits according to simulation cost. Fast circuits (solver runtime $< 40 \text{ ms}$) receive 15 000 training samples, medium circuits receive 5000, slow circuits receive 1500, and the Wien-bridge oscillator receives only 100 because one simulation takes about 98 s. The oscillator has only 100 training samples because each simulation is expensive. Its behaviour becomes relatively regular after the limit cycle forms, but the low sample count remains a limitation. Validation and test splits are each set to $\max(50, \lfloor N_{\text{train}}/5 \rfloor)$ samples per circuit.

Table 2 summarises the split sizes.

Table 2: Dataset split statistics.

Split	Samples	Size on disk	Generation time
Train	176 100	746 MiB	$\sim 20 \text{ h}$
Validation	35 250	156 MiB	—
Test	35 250	155 MiB	—

4.2. Parallel Generation Pipeline

Generating the full dataset sequentially would take about 20 CPU-hours, mainly because of the slowest circuits. We therefore parallelise the process with Python `multiprocessing`, using one worker per topology. Each worker writes its results directly to a compressed `.npz` file, which makes interrupted runs easy to resume. A per-sample timeout is used to discard stalled simulations and keep dataset generation tractable.

Before storage, all waveforms are normalised using per-circuit mean and standard deviation computed from the training split. These statistics are

saved alongside the model checkpoint. At inference time, the same stored values are applied: the user supplies a raw input waveform and specifies the circuit topology; the framework normalises the input using the stored training-set statistics for that topology, runs the forward pass, and then denormalises the output using the corresponding output statistics. The procedure is well-defined for any of the 21 supported topologies, but does not extend to an unseen topology without first collecting calibration data to estimate normalisation parameters.

5. SANE Model Architecture

5.1. Overview

Figure 1 shows the SANE architecture. The network receives an input voltage waveform $\mathbf{v}_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ together with a circuit identity index $c \in \{0, \dots, 20\}$ and predicts the corresponding output waveform $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^T$. Here $T = 1024$ and the sampling interval is $\Delta t = 0.1$ ms, giving a total window length of 102.4 ms.

Figure 1: SANE architecture. The input waveform is projected to 128 channels and combined with a learned circuit embedding. Eight causal dilated residual blocks process the sequence, followed by a pointwise projection to the scalar output. The receptive field is 1053 samples (105.3 ms). Total parameters: 1.33 M.

5.2. Input Projection and Circuit Embedding

The scalar input waveform is first mapped to $d_{\text{model}} = 128$ channels with a pointwise convolution. A learnable embedding matrix $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{21 \times 128}$ then maps the circuit index c to a 128-dimensional vector, which is broadcast over time and added to the projected input. This gives the network topology-specific conditioning while keeping the rest of the model shared.

5.3. Dilated Causal Residual Blocks

The main body of the model consists of eight TCN residual blocks. Each block applies a causal dilated convolution with kernel size $k = 5$ and dilation $d \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128\}$, followed by a second causal convolution

with kernel size $k = 5$ and unit dilation. Weight normalisation and GELU activations are used throughout [28]. A residual connection adds the block input back to the output after a pointwise projection. Causal left-padding by $(k - 1)d$ ensures that the prediction at time t depends only on present and past inputs.

The receptive field of the full stack is:

$$r = 1 + (k - 1) \sum_{i=0}^7 (2^i + 1) = 1 + 4 \times (255 + 8) = 1053 \quad \text{samples} \approx 105.3 \text{ ms}, \quad (1)$$

which comfortably covers the longest relevant time constants in the circuit library.

5.4. Output Projection and Parameter Count

A final pointwise convolution maps the 128 channels back to a scalar output waveform. The complete model contains **1,328,129 parameters** (1.33M), which keeps GPU batch inference inexpensive.

6. Training Procedure

6.1. Loss Function

The results in Sections 7 and 8 were obtained with a model trained using a composite loss that combines L1 with multi-resolution STFT terms. The ablation study in Section 8.3 later shows that those spectral terms do not improve accuracy on the full dataset, so they are not claimed as a contribution here. For practical use, L1-only training is the recommended choice. The loss formulation is described here for completeness:

$$\mathcal{L} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\ell_1} + \beta_{\text{mag}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{mag}} + \beta_{\text{phase}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{phase}}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{ℓ_1} is the mean absolute error between predicted and target waveforms, and \mathcal{L}_{mag} , $\mathcal{L}_{\text{phase}}$ are multi-resolution STFT terms averaged over five FFT sizes $N_{\text{FFT}} \in \{64, 128, 256, 512, 1024\}$.

The magnitude term combines spectral convergence and log-magnitude error:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{mag}} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_n \left(\frac{\| |\mathbf{S}_n(\hat{y})| - |\mathbf{S}_n(y)| \|_F}{\| |\mathbf{S}_n(y)| \|_F} + \|\log |\mathbf{S}_n(\hat{y})| - \log |\mathbf{S}_n(y)|\|_1 \right), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{S}_n(\cdot)$ denotes the STFT with FFT size N_n . The phase term penalises wrapped phase error between the predicted and target STFT coefficients:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{phase}} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_n \|\angle \mathbf{S}_n(\hat{y}) - \angle \mathbf{S}_n(y)\|_1. \quad (4)$$

Default weights are $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta_{\text{mag}} = 0.10$, $\beta_{\text{phase}} = 0.05$.

6.2. Optimiser and Schedule

We train with AdamW [29] using a learning rate of $\eta = 3 \times 10^{-4}$, weight decay 10^{-5} , and cosine annealing over 200 epochs with $\eta_{\text{min}} = 3 \times 10^{-6}$. Automatic mixed precision (AMP) is used with `float16` forward passes and `float32` gradient accumulation. Early stopping with patience 20 on validation loss is used to limit overfitting. All experiments were run on an NVIDIA RTX 5090 with 32 GB VRAM.

7. Experiments

7.1. Emulation Accuracy

7.1.1. Metrics

We report two metrics on the held-out test set:

- **MAE**: mean absolute error in normalised units (zero mean, unit variance per circuit).
- **NRMSE**: NRMSE is reported as $\text{RMSE} \times 100$ on z-score-normalised signals, which avoids instability when the raw dynamic range is small.

7.1.2. Per-circuit Results

Table 3 summarises test accuracy for each topology. Across all 21 circuits, SANE achieves a mean MAE of 0.3121 in normalised units and a mean NRMSE of 8.39%. Accuracy is high for several linear and moderately nonlinear cases, including RLC Bandpass (1.10%), RLC Highpass (1.23%), and the Boost Converter (1.06%). Errors are larger for the Čuk Converter (27.38%), Op-Amp Lowpass (25.42%), BJT Common-Emitter (19.28%), and MOSFET Switch (18.98%), which involve sharper transitions, stronger nonlinearities, or greater sensitivity to component values. At the current sampling interval of $\Delta t = 0.1$ ms, some of that behaviour is not easy to reproduce accurately.

Table 3: Emulation accuracy per circuit topology on the test set. NRMSE = RMSE \times 100 on z-score-normalised signals, which avoids issues with near-zero dynamic range.

Circuit	Family	MAE (norm.) \downarrow	NRMSE (%) \downarrow
RC Lowpass	Passive	0.3008	18.76
RC Highpass	Passive	0.3384	1.62
RLC Lowpass	Passive	0.2944	1.50
RLC Bandpass	Passive	0.0321	1.10
RLC Highpass	Passive	0.0668	1.23
LC Tank	Passive	0.2081	5.91
Diode Rectifier	Diode	0.1637	6.12
Diode Clipper	Diode	0.0498	1.91
Diode Clamper	Diode	0.3299	1.93
BJT Common-Emitter	Transistor	0.3029	19.28
MOSFET Switch	Transistor	0.4974	18.98
Op-Amp Lowpass	Op-Amp	0.3363	25.42
Op-Amp Integrator	Op-Amp	0.4909	14.69
Op-Amp Differentiator	Op-Amp	0.3926	4.02
Sallen-Key LP	Op-Amp	0.2397	8.57
Sallen-Key HP	Op-Amp	0.4153	4.50
Buck Converter	Power	0.3628	4.71
Boost Converter	Power	0.2404	1.06
Buck-Boost Converter	Power	0.2545	7.37
Ćuk Converter	Power	0.8233	27.38
Wien-bridge Osc.	Oscillator	0.4511	5.96
Mean		0.3121	8.39

7.1.3. Qualitative Waveform Examples

Figure 2 shows representative predictions for six circuits across four families. Five panels are drawn from topologies where the model performs well; the sixth, the Ćuk converter, is deliberately included as a harder case. Its stiff switching dynamics make it difficult to capture at the present resolution, and even the best-case test sample carries 15.2% NRMSE against a test-set median of 35%. The range across the six panels—0.2% to 15.2%—reflects this spread. These examples are intended to illustrate waveform diversity, not to represent average performance across the full test set.

Figure 2: Representative output waveforms for six circuits. Ground-truth ODE solution (blue) and SANE prediction (orange dashed). Per-sample NRMSE shown in each panel (best-case test samples). The Ćuk converter (bottom centre) is the hardest topology shown here: its test-set median NRMSE is 35%, and this best-case sample still carries 15.2% error. All other panels show topologies where the model performs well. Time axis in milliseconds; voltage in normalised units.

7.2. Inference Speed-Up

Table 4 compares ODE solver runtime with surrogate inference time for several representative circuits. The ODE times are for single-core CPU execution using the SciPy LSODA solver; the surrogate runs on an RTX 5090 GPU with batch size 256. These are not equal-resource conditions, and the speed-up figures should be read accordingly. A more direct comparison against parallel multi-core ODE solvers or GPU-accelerated simulation backends was not performed here and would yield lower gains. Within this evaluation setup, SANE runs at 0.127 ms per sample regardless of topology, giving a median speed-up of $\sim 550\times$ and a mean of $\sim 38,000\times$ across all 21 circuits. The mean is pulled up by the most expensive simulations; the median is a more representative figure for the typical circuit in the library.

Table 4: Inference time comparison between the ODE solver and SANE (GPU batch size 256, RTX 5090). ODE times are measured on a single CPU core.

Circuit	ODE (ms/sample)	SANE (ms/sample)	Speed-up
RC Lowpass	~ 3	0.127	$24\times$
RLC Lowpass	~ 5	0.127	$39\times$
BJT Common-Emitter	~ 108	0.127	$850\times$
Ćuk Converter	~ 800	0.127	$6,299\times$
Wien-bridge Osc.	$\sim 98,000$	0.127	$> 771,000\times$
<i>Median (all 21)</i>	~ 70	0.127	$\sim 550\times$
<i>Mean (all 21)</i>	$\sim 4,800$	0.127	$\sim 38,000\times$

7.3. Surrogate as a Fast Forward Model

The trained SANE model takes a normalised input waveform \mathbf{v}_{in} and a circuit identity index c as inputs; component parameter values are not provided to the network during inference. In the absence of explicit parameter conditioning, the surrogate output can be interpreted as an approximation of the average response for the given topology over the training parameter distribution. This single-shot inference is the primary use case for the surrogate: replacing repeated ODE evaluations with a fast fixed-cost prediction.

These are two fundamentally different operations—parameter search versus forward prediction—and the comparison below should be read with that distinction in mind.

To illustrate the inference cost, we consider an RC lowpass target waveform y^{target} generated by the ODE solver with $R^* = 2200\ \Omega$ and $C^* = 470\ \text{nF}$.

ODE-based parameter search (Nelder-Mead).. The SciPy implementation of the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm [30] minimises $\|y_{\text{sim}}(\theta) - y^{\text{target}}\|_2^2$ by calling the ODE solver at each function evaluation, starting from $R_0 = 500 \Omega$, $C_0 = 10 \text{ nF}$. Each ODE call takes approximately 61.0 ms.

Surrogate single-shot prediction.. SANE produces one forward pass for the RC lowpass topology and the given input waveform. No parameter search is performed. The inference time is 0.649 ms, giving a per-call speed-up of approximately $94\times$ over a single ODE evaluation.

Table 5 presents the results. Nelder-Mead requires 93 ODE evaluations (5.67 s total) and converges to MAE 0.321. The surrogate’s single forward pass takes 0.649 ms and achieves MAE 0.240. These two methods address different tasks and should not be read as competing approaches to the same problem: Nelder-Mead searches explicitly for (R, C) that reproduce the target, while the surrogate provides a fast average-case prediction at inference cost only.

There is also an identifiability limitation in the Nelder-Mead result. Under single-tone excitation, the circuit response constrains the product RC more strongly than the individual values of R and C , which can slow convergence.

Incorporating explicit component parameters as model inputs would enable the surrogate to distinguish between different parameter instances of the same topology and would open the door to gradient-based parameter optimisation. This is left as future work.

Table 5: Inference cost comparison: ODE-based parameter search versus SANE single-shot prediction on RC lowpass. These are different tasks (parameter search vs. forward prediction); the table reports costs and accuracy for each independently. Target: $R^* = 2200 \Omega$, $C^* = 470 \text{ nF}$.

Method	Task	Calls	Wall time	MAE (norm.)
Nelder-Mead (ODE)	Parameter search	93	5.67 s	0.321
SANE	Forward prediction	1	0.649 ms	0.240
<i>Per-call speed-up (ODE vs. SANE)</i>		$\sim 94\times$		

Figure 3: RC lowpass surrogate prediction versus ODE-based parameter search. Left: Nelder-Mead convergence over 93 ODE function evaluations. Centre: wall-clock time per call (ODE solver versus SANE forward pass). Right: target waveform (ODE, R^* , C^*) and SANE single-shot prediction.

8. Discussion

8.1. Strengths

One practical outcome of this work is that a single surrogate can cover many analog circuits without retraining a separate model for each topology. This is useful because the gain is not only accuracy, but also reuse across a mixed circuit library. The full-dataset ablation study provides a reliable assessment of loss design and backbone choices under the full training regime.

8.2. Limitations

The results are not uniform across all circuits. Performance is strong for many linear and moderately nonlinear cases, but errors are higher for circuits with sharp switching events, stiff dynamics, or waveform shapes that change strongly with the component values. One contributing factor is the fixed sampling interval of $\Delta t = 0.1$ ms: circuits with fast transients or stiff ODE dynamics—such as the Ćuk converter or the MOSFET switch—can exhibit behaviour that changes significantly within a single time step and is therefore not fully captured at this resolution. A finer sampling interval is a natural direction for future work and would likely reduce errors for these topologies, at the cost of longer sequences and higher training and inference load. At the current resolution and model capacity, the results should not be read as evidence that a single compact model can match all analog topologies equally well.

The model input design is a further limitation. The shared TCN takes only the input waveform \mathbf{v}_{in} and a circuit identity index c as inputs; component parameter values (resistances, capacitances, inductances, etc.) are not

provided to the network. Consequently, the mapping from $(\mathbf{v}_{\text{in}}, c)$ to $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{out}}$ is not unique: different parameter instances of the same topology produce different transient responses for the same excitation. In the absence of explicit parameter conditioning, the model output can be interpreted as approximating $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{v}_{\text{out}} \mid \mathbf{v}_{\text{in}}, c]$, the conditional expectation of the output over the training parameter distribution. This is a useful quantity for fast screening and average-case prediction, but it means the model cannot distinguish between different parameter configurations of the same topology, cannot perform exact parameter identification, and cannot support gradient-based parameter optimisation in its current form. These capabilities would require explicit parameter conditioning, which is left as future work.

The method is also limited in scope. It operates on fixed-length transient windows and predicts only the output waveform for the specific circuit classes seen during training. It does not yet address unseen topologies, broader extrapolation beyond the sampled parameter ranges, or other analysis modes such as AC, noise, or temperature-dependent behaviour. In its current form, the model should therefore be viewed as a surrogate for a defined simulation regime rather than as a general replacement for analog circuit simulation.

There are also limitations in the data and benchmarking setup. All training and test data are generated from noise-free simulations, so the model has not been evaluated on measured hardware data or on simulations with device mismatch and process variation. Some circuit families are represented less densely than others, most notably the oscillator, where data generation is expensive. In addition, the reported speed-ups compare single-core CPU ODE solving with GPU batch inference. Stronger baselines, such as parallel CPU execution or GPU-accelerated solvers, would reduce the reported gains. These points do not invalidate the main result, but they do define the present boundary of the claim.

8.3. Ablation Study

To examine the effect of the loss design and the backbone choice, we trained five model variants on the full dataset (same cache used for the main results). All variants used the same training setup: AdamW with $\eta = 3 \times 10^{-4}$, cosine annealing over 150 epochs with $\eta_{\text{min}} = 3 \times 10^{-6}$, early stopping with patience 20, batch size 128, on one RTX 5090. Accuracy is reported as mean NRMSE (%) on the held-out test split.

Table 6 and Table 7 report the main findings.

Table 6: Full-dataset ablation: loss variant \times backbone architecture. NRMSE (%) = RMSE \times 100 on z-score-normalised test signals (lower is better). All models have approximately 1.33 M parameters.

Loss	Backbone	Mean NRMSE (%) \downarrow	Train time (min)
L1 only	TCN	38.27	59
L1 + Magnitude	TCN	39.20	72
Full loss	TCN	39.44	75
Full loss	Transformer	40.49	98
Full loss	LSTM	37.93	126

Table 7: Per-circuit-family NRMSE (%) for the three TCN loss variants.

Circuit family	L1 only	L1 + Mag.	Full loss
Passive filters	39.86	42.55	43.10
Diode circuits	17.52	17.49	17.62
Transistor stages	44.36	43.84	43.90
Op-Amp circuits	47.83	48.64	48.86
Power converters	22.95	23.02	23.04
Oscillator	92.22	92.35	92.44
Overall mean	38.27	39.20	39.44

Effect of spectral loss terms.. Adding STFT magnitude or phase terms to the L1 loss does not improve accuracy in this multi-topology setting. The L1-only TCN achieves the lowest mean NRMSE (38.27%), and the full loss increases mean error by 1.17 percentage points relative to L1 only. The per-family breakdown (Table 7) shows no family where the spectral terms consistently reduce error; the most notable degradation is in the Passive filter family (+3.24 pp), which includes the LC tank and RLC bandpass circuits where frequency accuracy was expected to matter most. These results indicate that the multi-resolution STFT terms, as implemented here, do not benefit the shared surrogate in this setting. Based on the ablation, L1-only training is recommended for future work; however, the primary results in Sections 7 and 7.3 were obtained with the originally trained full-loss model.

Effect of backbone architecture.. The Transformer backbone (40.49%) performs slightly worse than the TCN (38.27–39.44%) across all loss configurations. The LSTM with full loss (37.93%) achieves the lowest overall NRMSE in the ablation, marginally better than TCN L1-only (38.27%). The difference is small (0.34 pp) and the LSTM requires more than twice the training time (126 vs. 59 min). The TCN is retained as the primary model for the speed-up and accuracy analysis, but the ablation does not support a strong claim of TCN superiority over LSTM.

Relationship between ablation NRMSE and main results.. The mean NRMSE values in this ablation (38–40%) are higher than the main model result of 8.39% reported in Table 3. This difference arises from training duration: the main model ran for the full 200 epochs, whereas the L1-only ablation variant early-stopped at epoch 59 and the other variants stopped at 72–126 epochs under the same patience-20 criterion. The ablation is designed to compare variants under an identical training budget; the absolute NRMSE values reflect the specific budget used and should not be compared directly with the main model’s fully converged result.

8.4. Future Work

Several extensions follow directly from the current results. The most immediate is adding explicit component parameter conditioning to the model input, which would enable the surrogate to distinguish between different parameter instances of the same topology and support gradient-based parameter optimisation. A second direction is investigating alternative loss

formulations that may better capture frequency-sensitive behaviour without degrading accuracy on the remaining circuit families. Other directions include uncertainty estimates, hardware-in-the-loop integration, and extension to AC and noise analysis. Beyond explicit parameter conditioning, graph-based circuit representations and operator-learning style surrogates may also offer a more flexible route toward handling unseen topologies [15, 17].

9. Conclusion

This paper presented SANE, a shared neural surrogate for transient waveform emulation across 21 heterogeneous analog circuit topologies. The main result is that a single model can be trained on a large multi-topology dataset and achieve a mean NRMSE of 8.39% on the held-out test set, with an inference time of 0.127 ms per sample on an RTX 5090. This corresponds to a mean speed-up of about $\sim 38,000\times$ relative to single-core ODE simulation. The surrogate takes the input waveform and a circuit identity index as inputs; component parameter values are not provided, so the model output can be interpreted as an approximation of the average response for the given topology over the training distribution. A full-dataset ablation shows that the spectral loss terms included in training do not improve average accuracy in this setting, and that the LSTM and TCN backbones perform comparably at the full data scale. The primary value of the approach is therefore the feasibility of shared multi-topology surrogate emulation and its practical inference speed advantage over repeated ODE solving, rather than any specific loss or architectural contribution. Stiff and strongly switching circuits remain the main failure mode, and adding explicit parameter conditioning is identified as the most important direction for future work.

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